

EXPERIENCE IN TREATING PATIENTS WITH PAPILOMAS OF THE NOSE AND SINUSES

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Abstract

Diagnostics and timely treatment of patients with tumorous processes of the nasal cavity and appendicular sinuses are of great clinical interest for otorhinolaryngologists. Papilloma is one of the most frequently encountered benign tumors of ENT organs. Currently, the effectiveness of various methods of treatment of HPV is 60-80%.

Key words: sinuses, nose, papilloma

Objective of the study was to study the effectiveness of tiloron (Lavomax) in the treatment of patients with papillomas of the nose and appendicular sinuses.

Material and methods of investigation: 66 patients with papillomas of the nose and appendicular sinuses were examined. The age of patients was 24 to 52 years, the disease was equally common in males 36 (54.5%) and females 30 (45.5%). All patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including a thorough history and ENT examination. All patients were divided into two groups: basic (34 patients) and control (32 patients). Patients in the main group received comprehensive therapy. After surgical treatment we used Lavomax under the following scheme: 0.125 g (1 tablet) per day for 2 days and further 0.125 g for 48 hours, for the course of treatment - 1.25 g (10 tablets).

Results of study. The positive clinical picture was accompanied by the improvement of immunological parameters. In 3 weeks of treatment in patients of the main group increase of T-lymphocytes from $50,6 \pm 2,1$ to $53,4 \pm 2,1\%$ occurred, with complete normalization in 28 patients (82,3%), while in the control group this index was normalized only in 20 patients (62,5%). Lavomax elevated the functional activity of T-helpers from $24,4 \pm 2,1$ to $40,2 \pm 2,5$ in the main group and from $26,4 \pm 2,0$ to $36,7 \pm 2,3$ in the control group. Lavomax had positive influence on humoral immunity, increasing the IgA level from $1,23 \pm 0,10$ g/l to $1,42 \pm 0,11$ g/l, in the control group this parameter didn't change considerably. The use of Lavomax allowed to reduce the number of relapses in the main group to 4,5% (one patient), whereas in the control group relapses occurred in 15% (3 patients).

Conclusions. Thus, the complex therapy with the use of tiloron (Lavomax) has shown its high efficiency due to which a rapid disappearance of clinical symptoms and normalization of immunological parameters of patients with nasal papilloma and paranasal sinuses have been observed. The results indicate the possibility of using tiloron (Lavomax) as an immunomodulatory drug in the complex treatment of papilloma of the nose and appendicular sinuses.

